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***Technical note on L2 performance for FOV widths 1.4 km
vs 1.5 km***

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<i>ESA Contract</i> 4000136480/21/N L/LF CCN1	<i>D09-05- L2 performance</i> <i>for FOV widths 1.4 km vs</i> <i>1.5 km</i>	<i>Contractor</i> <i>Karlsruhe Institute of</i> <i>Technology</i>
<p>This deliverable explains the change of uncertainty (spectral noise) introduced when a SEDF width of 1.5 km instead of 1.4 km is applied.</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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1 Introduction

The change of uncertainty (spectral noise) introduced when a SEDF width of 1.5 km instead of 1.4 km is applied.

2 Method

- The instrument simulator of the linear performance estimator chain is used to apply a Gaussian SEDF with FWHM of 1.5 km instead of 1.4 km to spectra and Jacobians for 1d error estimation. All other instrumental geometrical parameters (1 km sampling tangent altitude distance at 5 km, 115 tangent altitudes up to 115 km), spectral noise, Norton-Beer strong apodisation are kept unchanged.
- Using these spectral data, 1d linear uncertainty estimation is applied for three cases of fixed vertical resolution (threshold, goal+0.5km, goal).

3 Results

Figure 1 - Figure 3 show the results as the ratios between spectral noise induced uncertainties in the temperature and species vertical profiles between 1.5 km and 1.4 km FWHM of the SEDF. The typical effect is an increase of the estimated uncertainty which is lowest for the threshold vertical resolution of about 5%, 10% for goal+0.5km and a very strong increase of >>20% for the goal resolution.

The motivation for this investigation was a possible reduction of the SEDF FWHM threshold requirement from 1.4 km (at 718 cm^{-1}) to 1.4 km (at 800 cm^{-1}) (for larger wavenumbers, the FWHM decreases since it is mainly determined by diffraction). This would then result increasingly larger values than 1.4 km FWHM at wavenumbers $< 780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, reaching about 1.5 km at 720 cm^{-1} . However, this would only affect a subset of L2a parameters.

When comparing the results of the uncertainty estimation with the spectral windows used (see Figure 4), the change of the requirement would mainly affect C₂H₂, HCN, PAN, ozone and temperature (above ~30 km altitude). Here C₂H₂ and HCN are no primary target species. For PAN, the major band is directly at the transition region, and thus also not strongly affected (if at all). For ozone, there are also many lines $> 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be used for the retrieval in case a 5-10% increase of estimated uncertainty should be avoided (see e.g. alternative window selectin shown in Figure 5). For temperature, the increase of estimated noise uncertainty of 5-10% above about 30-50 km altitude is equal to about 0.1-0.2 K if the uncertainty would be 2 K.

Figure 1 Spectral noise-induced uncertainty for CAIRT target L2a parameters: ratio between noise-uncertainty in case of 1.5 km SEDF FWHM versus 1.4 km FWHM for fixed threshold vertical resolution of L2a product profiles.

SEDF-FWHM noise 1.5km/1.4km fovtest_gaslist1_april+45_mwCAIRTstd_OFFvw_vresgoalplus500m.png

Figure 2 As Figure 1 but for a vertical resolution of goal values + 0.5 km.

Figure 3 As Figure 1 but for a vertical resolution of goal values.

Figure 4 Altitude-dependent spectral windows used for retrievals. X-axis: wavenumber (cm^{-1}), y-axis: tangent altitude (km).

Figure 5 Alternative spectral window database selected only optimizing spectral noise uncertainty.